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New records of the hoverflies (Diptera: Syrphidae) from Russia

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Prokhorov, A. V. New records of the hoverflies (Diptera: Syrphidae) from Russia. — Two species of the hoverflies, *Chalcosyrphus eunotus* (Loew, 1873) and *Xanthogramma dives* (Rondani, 1857), were collected in Moscow Region and recorded from Russia for the first time. *Platycheirus jaerensis* Nielsen, 1971 was confirmed for Russian fauna. A summarized distributions and diagnosis of *P. jaerensis* and *X. dives* are provided.

Key words: Diptera, Syrphidae, *Chalcosyrphus eunotus*, *Platycheirus jaerensis*, *Xanthogramma dives*, Russia.

Прохоров, О. В. Нові знахідки мух-повисюх (Diptera: Syrphidae) з Росії. — Два види мух-повисюх, *Chalcosyrphus eunotus* (Loew, 1873) і *Xanthogramma dives* (Rondani, 1857), знайдено у Московській області та вперше відмічено для фауни Росії. Підтверджено наявність у фауні Росії *Platycheirus jaerensis* Nielsen, 1971. Узагальнено відомості про поширення видів та надано діагнози *P. jaerensis* і *X. dives*.

Ключові слова: Diptera, Syrphidae, *Chalcosyrphus eunotus*, *Platycheirus jaerensis*, *Xanthogramma dives*, Росія.

Прохоров, А. В. Новые находки мух-журчалок (Diptera: Syrphidae) из России. — Два вида мух-журчалок, *Chalcosyrphus eunotus* (Loew, 1873), и *Xanthogramma dives* (Rondani, 1857), пойманные в Московской области, впервые отмечены для России. Подтверждено наличие в фауне России *Platycheirus jaerensis* Nielsen, 1971. Обобщены сведения о распространении видов и даны диагнозы *P. jaerensis* и *X. dives*.

Ключевые слова: Diptera, Syrphidae, *Chalcosyrphus eunotus*, *Platycheirus jaerensis*, *Xanthogramma dives*, Россия.

Introduction

Barkalov & Mutin (2018) recorded 20 species of the genus *Chalcosyrphus* Curran, 1925 in the Russian fauna, of them seven species are known from Moscow Region (Violovitsh, 1935; Zimina, 1957, 1968, 1986). In present paper, one more species, *Chalcosyrphus eunotus* (Loew, 1873), is added to the list of the fauna of Russia.

The genus *Platycheirus* Lepeletier & Serville, 1828 is one of the largest genera of the hoverflies in the world, and 73 species of the genus are recorded from Russia (Barkalov & Mutin, 2018), plus one more species, *Platycheirus aurolateralis* Stubbs, 2002 (Prokhorov, 2018). Of them, 17 *Platycheirus* species have been recorded from Moscow Region (Violovitsh, 1935; Stackelberg, 1958; Zimina, 1968, 1981, 1986; Prokhorov, 2018). While studying hoverflies in Tabolovo (Moscow Region), moreover, *Platycheirus jaerensis* Nielsen, 1971 was collected the same time and the same place as *P. aurolateralis*.

Of the genus *Xanthogramma* Schiner, 1860, eight species are known from Russia (Barkalov & Mutin, 2018), and only three species were recorded from Moscow Region so far (Violovitsh, 1935; Chernov, 1958; Zimina, 1986): *Xanthogramma citrofasciatum* (De Geer, 1776), *X. laetum* (Fabricius, 1794) and *X. pedissequum* (Harris, 1776). It is quite obvious that *X. dives* (Rondani, 1857) was neither distinguished from similar species nor mentioned on species lists before the recent publication on this genus (Nedeljković *et al.*, 1918), in which new species concepts were supported by morphological and molecular evidences. The only specimen of *X. dives* was collected in Tabolovo (Moscow Region), and now we consider the range of this species to include Russia.

Some examined specimens of *Platycheirus jaerensis* were noted from Russia by Young *et al.* (2016), but without localities. However, *P. jaerensis* as well as *Chalcosyrphus*

eunotus, was indicated as “species of which presence in the territory of Russia is doubtful” (Barkalov & Mutin, 2018). Therefore, the records of these species require confirmation as well as the record of *X. dives*.

Material and methods

All specimens of the examined material are deposited in I. I. Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine (Kyiv).

The morphological terminology follows Cumming & Wood (2017). Diagnoses are generally based on the keys by Bartsh *et al.* (2009), Van Veen (2010), and Nedeljković *et al.* (1918).

Photos of the specimens were taken using a Canon PowerShot A640 camera mounted on Carl Zeiss Stemi 2000 binocular microscope, and then subsequently combined with Helicon Focus (version 6.0.18) and processed in Adobe Photoshop CS6 by the author.

Results

Subfamilia Eristalinae

Tribe Milesiini

Subtribe Xylotina

Chalcosyrphus (Xylotodes) eunotus (Loew, 1873) (Fig. 1)

Material examined. Russia: Moscow Region, Tabolovo env., 55.9149N 36.0686E, clearing in mixed forest, 8.06.2019, 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution: Armenia, Belgium, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, North Macedonia, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Slovak Republic, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine (Peck, 1988; Dirickx, 1994; Holinka & Mazánek, 1997; Vujić & Milankov, 1999; Carrières, 2001; Stubbs & Falk, 2002; Stănescu & Pârnu, 2005; Mielczarek, 2009; Reemer *et al.*, 2009; Tóth, 2011; Williams *et al.*, 2011; Saribiyik, 2014; Van Steenis *et al.*, 2015; Ricarte & Marcos-García, 2017; Prokhorov *et al.*, 2018; Speight, 2018; Syrphidae checklists, 2019); Russia (**first record**).

Note. Despite its wide distribution, *C. eunotus* is rare throughout its range. In Great Britain, this species is listed under the UK Biodiversity Action Plan and qualifies as Nationally Scarce (Ball & Morris, 2014).

Subfamilia Syrphinae

Tribe Bacchini

Platycheirus (Platycheirus) jaerensis Nielsen, 1971 (Figs 2–4)

Material examined. Russia: Moscow Region, Tabolovo env., 55.9153N 36.0485E, in the garden, 30.07.2018, on flowers of *Angelica sylvestris*, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution: Estonia, Finland, France (Jura), Germany, Hungary, Latvia, Norway, Sweden, Switzerland; Alaska and Canada in N America (Peck, 1988; Tóth, 2011; Haarto & Kerppola, 2014; Young *et al.*, 2016; Speight, 2018; Syrphidae checklists, 2019); Russia (**first record**).

Diagnosis. *Platycheirus jaerensis* belongs to the *P. peltatus* group (Van Steenis & Goeldlin de Tiefenau, 1998; Bartsh *et al.*, 2009; Young *et al.*, 2016). In Europe, **female** of this species is most similar to *P. amplus* Curran, 1927, *P. holarcticus* Vockeroth, 1990, *P. peltatus* (Meigen, 1822) and *P. nielsenii* Vockeroth, 1990 in having fore and mid femora entirely yellow (in similar *P. islandicus* Ringdahl, 1930 and *P. parmatus* Romani, 1857, fore and mid femora with a broad black ring). *Platycheirus jaerensis* can be separated from *P. amplus* and *P. holarcticus* by tergite 2 with large rhomboid maculae (Fig. 2) that reach or almost reach the anterior corners of the tergite (in *P. amplus* and *P. holarcticus*, tergite 2 with small lunular to reniform maculae that not reach the anterior corners of the tergite). From similar *P. peltatus* (Figs 5–7) and *P. nielsenii* it can be clearly distinguished by the yellow scape and pedicel (Figs 3, 4) (in *P. peltatus* and *P. nielsenii*, scape and often pedicel black, as on Figs 6, 7); paired yellow abdominal maculae at most with faint silvery pruinescence (in *P. peltatus* and *P. nielsenii*, paired yellow abdominal maculae with heavy silvery pruinescence). These characters were based on Bartsh *et al.* (2009) and Van Veen (2010).

Tribe Syrphini

Xanthogramma dives (Rondani, 1857) (Fig. 8)

Material examined. Russia: Moscow Region, Tabolovo env., 55.913381N 36.068807E, edge of mixed forest, 17.06.2017, on flowers of *Anthriscus sylvestris*, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution: at present uncertain, due to confusion with *X. pedissequum* (Harris, 1776) and *X. stackelbergi* Violovitsh, 1975, but authentically known from Andorra, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Slovak Republic, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland (Belcari *et al.*, 1995; De Groot & Govedič, 2008; Mielczarek, 2009; Tóth, 2011; Van Eck, 2011; Van Steenis, 2011; Ricarte & Marcos-García, 2017; Nedeljković *et al.*, 1918; Speight, 2018; Syrphidae checklists, 2019); Ukraine (Prokhorov *et al.*, in press), Russia (**first record**).

Diagnosis. Three species of the genus, *X. dives*, *X. pedissequum* and *X. stackelbergi*, are very similar in

Fig. 1. *Chalcosyrphus eunotus*, female, habitus, dorsal view.

appearance. Common characters for them are: the tergite 2 wider than long; alula entirely covered in microtrichia; eye pile very sparse, shorter than the diameter of the anterior ocellus; hind femora black on the apical fourth. *Xanthogramma dives* can be easily separated from *X. pedissequum* by the thorax with more than two yellow maculae laterally (in *X. pedissequum*, thorax with one or two yellow maculae laterally). From *X. stackelbergi*, it can be distinguished by wing cells r_1 and r_{2+3} darkened in the apical part (in *X. stackelbergi*, wing cells r_1 and r_{2+3} hyaline in the apical part). These characters are based on Nedeljković *et al.* (1918).

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Figs 2–7. *Platycheirus jaerensis* (figs 2–4) and *P. peltatus* (figs 5–7), females: 2, 5 — habitus, dorsal view; 3, 6 — head, frontal view; 4, 7 — antenna, lateral view.

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Fig. 8. *Xanthogramma dives*, female, habitus, dorsal view.

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